

Collaborative Networked Organizations and Virtual Customer Communities: Crafting the Value Co-Creation to Enhance Marketing Performance

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Abstract

This article purposed to analyze the influence of Collaborative Networked Organizations and Virtual Customer Communities (VCC) in increasing the co creation towards marketing performance enhancement during pandemic. Population in this article is the manufacture in Semarang central java which has networking and collaboration strategy with other groups of common interest. Sample technique used in this article is census, which mean that the entire population is used as sample. The sample in this study were 152 companies in Semarang, Central Java. Data collected analyzed with Sem Amos statistic software analysis. The result shows that Collaborative Networked Organizations (CNOs) demonstrate high potential as drivers of shared value creation, enabling organizations to access new knowledge, share risks and resources, combine complementary skills and capacities, enabling them to focus on their core competencies. Virtual Customer Communities have a positive and significant effect on Value Co-Creation. Virtual Customer Communities s can be seen as a cooperative process of value co-creation. Collaborative Networked Organization and virtual Customer Communities has no effect on Marketing Performance. Value Co-Creation has a positive and significant effect on Marketing Performance. In value co-creation context, strategies and business models are continuously shaped over time in a discovering process of new sources of value and new opportunities and ways for co-creating it by / for the customers and stakeholders in the short- and long-term.

Keywords: *Collaborative Networked Organizations, Virtual Customer Communities, Value Co-Creation, Marketing Performance.*

INTRODUCTION

In today's global economy, organizations are increasingly required to collaborate and engage in new forms of highly collaborative mechanisms and network structures that are able to provide a competitive advantage by combining the best skills or core competencies and resources of several organizations, in order to create a more value proposition. attractive and relevant to the needs and expectations of consumers. Collaborative Networked Organizations (CNOs) potentially show as a driver of co-creation, enabling organizations to access new knowledge, share risks and resources, combine complementary skills and capacities, enabling them to focus on their core competencies [1]. Collaborative Networked Organizations (CNOs) drive innovation, and thus create new sources of value through confrontation of ideas and practices, combination of resources and technology, and creation of synergies [2]. Virtual Customer Communities (VCC) demonstrate promising (business) value as " an online social network "capable of leveraging all aspects of a product or service, from product design and marketing communications to creating an overall experience [3].

Online communication technology is increase the new forms of social community exposure, which are often called virtual communities, with the ability to engage customers in ongoing dialogue with other customers as well as with companies [4]. Leveraging a customer-based value creation system providing a way to interact, learn, conduct transactions, and share valuable knowledge with all parties involved in the development and use of products and services [5]. Current customer engagement trends will continue to evolve in the following years, changing the role of customers from pure consumers of products and services to partners in the value creation process, and as a result organizational structures and business models will migrate to new strategic alliances [3].

Global competition, market dynamism, and advances in information and communication technologies are opening and challenging new ways of creating value. Organisations nowadays must continually disintegrate and reintegrate themselves in order to quickly and continually assess their value-chain capabilities for a fast response to the rapidly evolving industry dynamics and customers' preferences [4].

The future belongs to companies that continue to generate new knowledge from customer experiences, and identify and enable new co-creation opportunities to support exciting experiential environments. Organization has to exposure their new strategy to increasing their resiliency in this pandemic era. They must adapt the new customer behaviour switch. Much research still needs to be done to close the interaction gap that is a major obstacle to effective customer engagement in communities in a collaborative networks to create the synergies needed as initial joint value creation strategies between organizations and customers. This article purposed to analyze the influence of Collaborative Networked Organizations and Virtual Customer Communities (VCC) in increasing the co creation towards marketing performance enhancement during pandemic.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Marketing Performance

Marketing performance is a measure of achievement of the company which includes all activities of the marketing process in a period of time [6]. Marketing performance can also be seen as a concept used to measure the extent to which market achievements have been achieved for a product produced by the company [7]. Marketing performance can be interpreted as a formof achievement measurement that can be obtained from a marketing activity within the company as a whole [8]. In addition, marketing performance can also be seen as the final concept used by companies in measuring the extent to which the company's products have achieved and the target market [9]. Marketing performance is a factor that is often used to measure the impact of the successful strategy implemented by the company [10]. The company's strategy is directed to produce better marketing performance such as sales volume and sales growth rate made by the company and good financial performance [11].

The three main values of marketing performance are sales value, sales growth and market shares [7]. The company's sales growth will depend on the number of customers as a whole who already know the constant average consumption level in purchases. Sales value shows how many rupiahs or units of product the company has sold to consumers or customers. The higher the sales value, the more products the company sells. Meanwhile, the market position shows how much the contribution of a product owned can dominate the market for similar types of products compared to those of competitors. Indicators that can be used in assessing marketing performance are sales volume, customer growth, and profitability [12].

Collaborative Networked Organisations

New challenges arise in supporting collaboration between organizations characterized by problems such as how organizations should share the same goals, build multiple levels of trust, agree on common practices and values, how to operate based on a common technology infrastructure and so on [13] Collaboration implies the sharing of risk, resources, responsibility and reward among organizations that act as joint entities (e.g. collaborative networks), to achieve common goals that would not be possible, or would have higher costs, if done individually (e.g. collaboration opportunity) [14]. Collaborative Networked Organizations (CNOs), or simply collaborative networks can be very large, geographically dispersed, and heterogeneous in terms of: their operating environment, culture, social capital and objectives; however, these organizations collaborate to achieve common or better compatible goals, and their interactions are supportive [13]. Especially in collaborative networks, readiness to collaborate means the leadership ability to support collaborative activities, allocate/assign resources (money, staff, technology, and information) across organizational boundaries, and adhere to common ground for successful collaboration (principles general operations, common ontology, operable infrastructure, and cooperation agreements) [4].

Collaborative networks consist of “different entities, most of them are autonomous, geographically distributed, and heterogeneous in terms of operating environment, culture, social capital, and different goals but still collaborate to achieve the same or better compatible goals, so that they can produce value together [15].

H₁: Collaborative Networked Organizations will increase value co-reation

Collaborative Networked Organizations (CNOs) consist of independent organizations that are linked by information techniques and work together to complete tasks, achieve common goals and serve customers for a certain period of time [16]. Collaborative Networked Organizations (CNOs) are indicated as specifications of rules, criteria for decision making, responsibilities, and boundaries for action and autonomy [1]. Collaborative Networked Organizations (CNOs) are also identified as the ability to adapt to environmental changes (market, technology), the need to cope with external changes through adequate levels of adaptation, and evolutionary development, which aims for continuous improvement [16]. Collaborative networked organisations can provide the basis for agility in dynamic and turbulent market conditions [15].

H₂: Collaborative Networked Organizations will increase marketing performance

Virtual Customer Community (VCC)

A virtual customer community is an “aggregation of individuals or business partners who interact based on a shared interest, where the interaction is at least partially supported or mediated by technology and guided by certain protocols and norms” [29]. We focus on firm-sponsored virtual customer communities that are characterized by two dimensions those are the sponsoring firm identifies it self as a sponsor by using its name or logos on the virtual customer community homepage and the firm that sponsors the virtual customer community also pursues commercially oriented goals within that community.

We conducted keyword searches on “virtual customer community” and related terms (virtual community, online community) in numerous peer-reviewed organization and communication outlets.

Virtual Customer Community devinited as a community composed of individuals who hold a shared interest around specific products and services and characterized by Customer interaction, Knowledge creation mechanism and Customer motivation [3]. Another scholar define Virtual Customer Community as a group of people with common interests and practices that communicate regularly and for some duration in an organized way over the internet through a common location or mechanism [17]. Organization can give and get information through the virtual customer community as a collection of online services that enabled firms to involve their customer in new product development activities, it indicated in three characteristics those are Customer interaction, Sense of identification with community and product involvement [17]. Virtual consumer community design features will influence customer value creation in new product development activities [3]. Virtual customer community characteristic influences customer beliefs about the organization, which influence trust in the community sponsor, which influence customer willingness to share personal information and cooperate in creating value [18].

H₃: Virtual consumer community will increase coalition with the organisations to the value creation

Firms can develop virtual customer communities that create opportunities to enhance their social capital and their vis-a-vis relationships with customers. Firms use virtual customer communities to create new knowledge by promoting customer contributions to the virtual customer community and to the company [42]. Firms can also design virtual customer communities that encourage customers to submit ideas for new products and services, creating knowledge that enhances a firm's ability to sense market opportunities [45]. Managing this type of virtual customer communities is beneficial for marketing, branding and advertisement activities [4].

H₄: Virtual consumer community will increase the marketing performance

Value Co Creation

Developed countries must continue to innovate to find new ways to add value to their products in order to preserve their organization [19]. Customers usually look for such values price, quality, speed, and customization of products and services however, customers in the technological era and knowledgeable seek different values, for example the experience of using a particular product or service, a sense of beauty, safety, comfort, affection for the product or the way they are buy [4]. Innovations that create new value must provide that experience to stakeholders.

Collaboration is very effective for value creation through products or services in new ventures, process innovations, and new business models [20]. Collaborative organizations are organizations that are innovative and efficient, agile and scalable [5]. Such organizations focus on knowledge production through internal and external collaboration. In the process of creating shared value, the company works closely with all stakeholders, especially customers. Customers fully understand what they want and how the product / service can be transformed to provide new values [21]. The core principle of shared value creation is "engaging people to create valuable experiences together" while enhancing the network economy, there are four elements that have been suggested for co-creation: experiential mindset, interaction context for collective intelligence, engagement platform, and network relationship [22]. Customer Value co creation provides new and better products/services for consumers, leading to broader customer bases, often supported through on-line purchasing and else enable organizations to produce and deliver these improved goods or services in more efficient [20].

H₅: Value Co Creation will increase the marketing performance.

METHOD

This article is an exploratory-research which aimed to find the relationship between variables independent and dependent variables. Population in this article is the manufacture in Semarang Central Java which has networking and collaboration strategy with other groups of common interest. Sample technique used in this article is census, which mean that the entire population is used as sample. The sample in this study were 152 companies in Semarang, Central Java. Data collected analyzed with Sem Amos statistic software analysis.

Districts	Industry Strata (Unit)			
	Big Size (> 99)		Medium Size (20-99)	
	2014	2010	2014	2010
Mijen	6,00	5,00	4,00	1,00
Gunungpati	1,00	1,00	5,00	6,00
Banyumanik	7,00	9,00	8,00	6,00
Gajahmungkur	-	-	-	1,00
Smg Selatan	2,00	1,00	3,00	5,00
Candisari	-	1,00	4,00	2,00
Tembalang	1,00	1,00	-	2,00
Pedurungan	14,00	7,00	18,00	15,00
Genuk	35,00	32,00	52,00	58,00
Gayamsari	1,00	2,00	5,00	4,00
Smg Timur	3,00	1,00	9,00	13,00
Smg Utara	12,00	13,00	14,00	12,00
Smg Tengah	6,00	3,00	8,00	10,00
Smg Barat	14,00	12,00	12,00	16,00
Tugu	24,00	24,00	14,00	5,00
Ngaliyan	26,00	23,00	20,00	22,00
Kota Semarang	152,00	135,00	176,00	178,00

Sources: BPS Semarang, 2019

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is used to test the research hypotheses that have been proposed in the previous chapter. This study uses two kinds of analysis techniques, namely: Confirmatory Factor Analysis and Weight Regression. Confirmatory factor analysis in SEM is used to confirm the most dominant factors in a group of variables. In this study, confirmatory factor analysis is used to test the indicators that make up the Collaborative Networked Strategy, Virtual Customer Communities, Value Co-Creation and Marketing Performance. Regression weight in SEM is used to examine how much influence the theoretical variables relationship has. In this study, regression weight was used to test the research hypothesis.

Confirmatory analysis of the latent variable forming indicators and reliability tests have been presented. The next analysis is the analysis of Structural Equal Modeling (SEM) on the whole model (full model). Goodness of fit evaluation is intended to assess how well the research model is being developed. The results of data processing for the full model SEM analysis are presented below:

Figure 1. Full Model Analysis

The results of the goodness of fit test of the full SEM model are presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1. Goodness of Fit Full Model SEM Test Results

Goodness of Fit Index	Criteria	Estimation Value	Result
Chi-Square (df=60)	Small (<79.08)	60.133	Good
Probabilitas	≥ 0,05	0.136	Good
CMIN/DF	≤ 2,00	1.069	Good
GFI	≥ 0,90	0.974	Good
AGFI	≥ 0,90	0.909	Good
TLI	≥ 0,95	0.936	Good
CFI	≥ 0,95	0.973	Good
RMSEA	≤ 0,08	0.077	Good

Based on the results of the feasibility test of the model presented in Table 1, it is known that the results of the estimated value of the chi square, probability, CMIN / DF, GFI, AGFI, TLI, CFI, and RMSEA criteria values are obtained on the good or fit criteria. On the basis of the test results, it can be said that there is a match between the input of observations and the predictions of the model formed and it can be concluded that this structural model is acceptable and can be continued in the next analysis.

The criteria for goodness of fit of the estimated structural model can be fulfilled, then the next stage is the analysis of the structural model relationship (hypothesis testing) as shown in Figure 4.2 previously. The relationship between constructs in the hypothesis is indicated by the value of regression weights. This analysis is used to test the research hypotheses proposed in the previous chapter. Hypothesis testing is seen based on the Critical Ratio (CR) value of a causality relationship. A relationship is said to be significant if the value of Critical Ratio (CR) > 1.96 is obtained or p value < 0.05. The results of SEM data processing with AMOS can be presented in the following.

Direct Effect Analysis

The magnitude of the direct effect is based on the results of the analysis carried out, it appears that the estimation results of the parameter values of the direct effect between the independent variables and the dependent variable. The estimated value of the path coefficient is known in Standardized Regression Weights. The results of the overall direct effect analysis are presented in Table 2 below:

Table 2. SEM Estimation Results of Parameters Direct Effect between Variables

1	Collaborative Networked Organization (X ₁)	Value Co-Creation (Y ₁)	0,381	2,654	0,014	Positive and significant
		Marketing Performance (Y ₂)	0,245	1,706	0,088	Not Significant
2	Virtual Customer Communities (X ₂)	Value Co-Creation (Y ₁)	0,539	2,698	0,007	Positive and significant
		Marketing Performance (Y ₂)	0,068	0,326	0,744	Not significant
3	Value Co-Creation (Y ₁)	Marketing Performance (Y ₂)	0,687	3,025	0,002	Positive significant

Referring to the test results of the overall model, a mathematical model equation can be written in the form of a Structural Equation Model (SEM) as follows:

$$Y_1 = 0,381 X_1 + 0,539 X_2 + \zeta_2 R^2 = 0,762 \quad (1)$$

$$Y_2 = 0,245 X_1 + 0,068 X_2 + 0,687 Y_1 + \zeta_2$$

$$R^2 = 0,860 \quad (2)$$

The mathematical equation model above can be explained as follows: In model (1), the coefficient of X₁ to Y₁ is 0.381, which means that each increase in the level of Collaborative Networked Organization by 1% will increase the Value Co-Creation score by 0.381 or 38.1%. The coefficient of X₂ to Y₁ is 0.539, which means that every 1% increase in the level of Virtual Customer Communities will increase the Value Co-Creation score by 0.539 or 53.9%.

In model (2), the coefficient of X₁ to Y₂ is 0.245, meaning that every 1% increase in the level of Collaborative Networked Organization will increase the Marketing Performance score by 0.245 or 24.5%. The coefficient of X₂ to Y₂ is 0.068, which means that every 1% increase in the level of Virtual Customer Communities will increase the Marketing Performance score

by 0.068 or 6.8%. The coefficient of Y1 to Y2 is 0.687 which means that each increase in the Value Co-Creation level of 1% will increase the Marketing Performance score by 0.687 or 68.7%.

The value of the coefficient of determination (R2) in the SEM model is called the square multiple correlation which can be explained as follows: Nilai squared multiple correlation pada persamaan pertama adalah 0,762 Nilai ini menunjukkan bahwa 76,2% dari variasi nilai Value Co-Creation dipengaruhi oleh adanya kontribusi variasi nilai variabel Collaborative Networked Organization dan Virtual Customer Communities.

The value of squared multiple correlation in the second equation is 0.860. This value indicates that 86.0% of the variation in the value of Marketing Performance is influenced by the contribution of the variation in the value of Collaborative Networked Organization, Virtual Customer Communities and Value Co-Creation variables.

Table 2 presents the direct effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables which can be explained as follows:

1. Hypothesis Testing 1. The first hypothesis examines the effect of Collaborative Networked Organization Strategy on Value Co-Creation. The test decision is if the Critical Ratio (CR) value > 1.96 or the p value < 0.05. Based on these criteria, because the CR value is 2.654 with a probability of 0.014. Therefore, the value of CR > 1.96 and p < 0.05, it is concluded that the Collaborative Networked Organization has a positive and significant effect on Value Co-Creation.
2. Hypothesis Testing 2. The second hypothesis examines the effect of Virtual Customer Communities on Value Co-Creation. The test decision is if the Critical Ratio (CR) value > 1.96 or the p value < 0.05. Based on these criteria, because the CR value is 2,698 with a probability of 0.007. Therefore, the value of CR > 1.96 and p < 0.05, it is concluded that Virtual Customer Communities have a positive and significant effect on Value Co-Creation.
3. Hypothesis Testing 3. The third hypothesis examines the effect of Collaborative Networked Organization on Marketing Performance. The test decision is if the Critical Ratio (CR) value > 1.96 or the p value < 0.05. Based on these criteria, because the CR value is 1.706 with a probability of 0.088. Therefore, the value of CR < 1.96 and p > 0.05, it is concluded that the Collaborative Networked Organization has no effect on Marketing Performance.
4. Hypothesis Testing 4. The fourth hypothesis examines the effect of Virtual Customer Communities on Marketing Performance. The test decision is if the Critical Ratio (CR) value > 1.96 or the p value < 0.05. Based on these criteria, because the CR value is 0.326 with a probability of 0.744. Because the value of CR < 1.96 and p > 0.05, it is concluded that Virtual Customer Communities has no effect on Marketing Performance.
5. Hypothesis Testing 5. The fifth hypothesis examines the effect of Value Co-Creation on Marketing Performance. The test decision is if the Critical Ratio (CR) value > 1.96 or the p value < 0.05. Based on these criteria, because the CR value is 3.025 with a probability of 0.002. Because the value of CR > 1.96 and p < 0.05, it is concluded that Value Co-Creation has a positive and significant effect on Marketing Performance.

Analysis of the indirect effect was conducted to determine the effect of the Collaborative Networked Organization and Virtual Customer Communities variables on the Marketing Performance variable through the intervening variable, namely Value Co-Creation. According to Ghazali (2011), testing the effect of intervening can be done using the Sobel test (Sobel Test). Based on the results of this analysis, the amount of the summary of the indirect effect test can be presented in table 3.

Table 3. Sobel Test

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Collaborative Networked Organization towards Marketing Performance through Value Co-Creation	0,258	1,995	0,046
Virtual CustomerCommunities toward Marketing Performance through Value Co-Creation	0,360	2,013	0,044

The results of the indirect effect test between variables based on the model and research results can be explained that there is a significant influence between the Collaborative Networked Organization variable on Marketing Performance through Value Co-Creation as evidenced by the C.R value of 1.995 and a probability value of 0.046. Thus, it can be concluded that Value Co-Creation mediates the Collaborative Networked Organization on Marketing Performance. There is a significant influence between the Virtual Customer Communities variable on Marketing Performance through Value Co-Creation as evidenced by the C.R value of 2.013 and a probability value of 0.044. Thus, it can be concluded that Value Co-Creation mediates the influence of Virtual Customer Communities on Marketing Performance.

Figure of Sobel Results the effect of Collaborative Networked Organization on Marketing Performance through Value Co-Creation:

Input:		Test statistic:	p-value:
t_a	2.654	Sobel test:	1.99500807
t_b	3.025	Aroian test:	1.93612561
		Goodman test:	2.05961176
		Reset all	Calculate

Figure 3. Sobel test Collaborative Networked Organization on Marketing Performance through Value Co-Creation

Input:		Test statistic:	p-value:
t_a	2.698	Sobel test:	2.01349615
t_b	3.025	Aroian test:	1.95488296
		Goodman test:	2.07771879
		Reset all	Calculate

Figure 4. Figure of Sobel Results the effect of Virtual Customer Communities on Marketing Performance through Value Co-Creation

Discussion

Collaborative Networked Organization has a positive and significant effect on Value Co-Creation. The use of a collaboration platform is intended to contribute to the network of all employees in the company. Collaborative Networked Organization create a digital workplace as an entry point into the corporate community, achieving greater efficiency by replacing a large number of similar applications running in parallel with a unified collaboration platform. By connecting all employees with the networked collaboration, communication is also enhanced and knowledge is made more available throughout the company as a result in social and community cohesion and create a share value creation. Collaborative Networked Organization forms a community providing access to various functions that are more closely integrated. Improved user-friendliness leads to intensive collaboration, for example, to more intensive use of web meetings. Beyond that, management completes a strictly defined documentation process or strict rules for cooperation and places greater emphasis on self-monitoring of employees and teams. In Collaborative Networked Organization where customer and organization is on a circle off connection, customer uses to create and shape his/her own personal experiences with their product providers by having access to a co-creation toolkit to construct their own experience outcomes by co-design and co-developing their own products. Moreover, it is important to recall at this point that ‘value co-creation’ is contextual, and therefore customers’ interactions are the key essentials in the value co-creation process with their product providers.

Virtual Customer Communities have a positive and significant effect on Value Co-Creation. Virtual environments offer new avenues for companies to increase their social capital vis-a-vis relationships with customers and to facilitate value creation. The focus on customers is not intended to undermine the usefulness of the virtual environment to drive value creation by other external entities, such as suppliers and complements; on the contrary, it only serves to demonstrate the power and potential of new technologies to facilitate distributed innovation involving the resources that are most distant from the company [23]. Virtual environments offer customers radically new ways to contribute to value creation. Customer engagement is seen as an organizational construct that includes the number and types of activities in which both entities are involved - below and above their regular economic transactions[3]. Current customer engagement trends will continue to evolve and changing the role of the customer from a purely product consumer to a partner in the value creation process. as a result, the organizational structure and business model will migrate to new strategic alliances and a collaborative model based on an open business model that will support the creation and operation of an adequate collaborative e-platform for shared value creation.

Collaborative Networked Organization has no effect on Marketing Performance. Value creation becomes much more dependent on intangibles such as knowledge, relationships and branding, and soon on experience. The use of “interaction maps” aimed at discovering key interaction points where companies can devise new or better interactions for improving dialogue, access to knowledge, mutual understanding of risks and transparency in the value co-creation process with their customers[4]. In Collaborative Networked Organization where customer and organization are on a circle off connection, customers’ interactions are the key essentials in the marketing of their product providers. Organization often supporting multiple interaction channels, and at the same time they facing losing customers when they cannot full fill the customer requirement based on a common view of his/her experience context. This will lead to a

soak relationship and will emerge bad reputation of their product. This will provide negative word of mouth and spreaded-fastly in social media and affect the marketing performance.

Virtual Customer Communities has no effect on Marketing Performance. Characteristics such as flexibility, agility, and adaptability are key factors in delivering customer value that are becoming increasingly complex, dynamic, and dependent on consumer expectations. Giving customers access to knowledge, tools, and expertise on the one hand will help organizations build on their own experiential outcomes, and it also challenges the idea that ownership is the only way for consumers to experience value by focusing on access to experiences across multiple experience gateways (point interaction), on the other hand, grows risk because it involves both parties, risk assessment assumes that if consumers become co-creators of value, they will demand more information about the potential risks associated with product development, but they also have to assume more responsibility for dealing with these risks[3]. Transparency of information in the interaction process will be indispensable for customers to participate effectively in the co-creation mode, and to build trust between organizations and consumers. But, in the other side, when customer in the networked feel disappointed with the product or the service they have got, they will give bad reaction, and will impact in the decrease of marketing performance.

Value Co-Creation has a positive and significant effect on Marketing Performance. Valueco-creationoccurs as actors such as networks of economic and social actors and integrate their resources with others' resources especially their knowledge, skills and competences. Value co-creation occurs when the organization interact and collaborate in providing product or service to their customers [24]. Value co-creation particularly encourages the interactions between the organisation in a collaborative network organization and their consumers [19]. The modern and digital environment promote high technological organization and allows consumers to determine the value of the product or service they received. The consumers do so by sharing their experience and also interact with the network of other business actors in this collaborative environment. Valueco-createdpossiblytheorganisationstoenter a new market with a lower cost), sharing risks and responsibilities, enhancing innovation capabilities, increasing flexibility, sharing resources and skills, increasing customer satisfaction, increasing efficient production, increasing productivity business performances [25], [26].

CONCLUSION

Collaborative Networked Organizations (CNOs) show high potential as drivers of shared value creation, enabling organizations to access new knowledge, share risks and resources, combine complementary skills and capacities, enabling them to focus on their core competencies. Virtual Customer Communities have a positive and significant effect on Value Co-Creation. Virtual Customer Communities s can be seen as a cooperative process of value co-creation. Value Co-Creation has a positive and significant effect on Marketing Performance.

Collaborative Networked Organizations (CNOs) represent a promising paradigm with the customer community to emphasize core competencies, personalization and innovation, supported by collaborative mechanisms, to enable consumers to tag products by their own applications, preferences and configurations, and thereby create shared value in collaborative endeavors. From the academic perspective, this paper identifies the key research themes of capabilities and value co-creation in digital based ecosystem. From a practical perspective, this research delivers useful research result for organization to engage the customer relationship to promote the value co creation. Organizations can occupy the model developed in the research to describe their capabilities status (e.g., business and digital capabilities), and to understand how these capabilities enable the value creation process. This research also informs organizations of the importance of value co-created through network collaborations with other organizations and also its customer and how it impacts on the existing capabilities. These elements are vital for organization to make an informed decision before making any strategic moves or interactions in business.

In value co-creation context, strategies and business models are continuously shaped over time in a discovering process of new sources of value and new opportunities and ways for co-creating it by/for the customers and stakeholders in the short- and long-term. Therefore, the strategy definition will be a process of continuous discovery, active learning and adaptation within an agile business ecosystem capable of accessing new competencies, rapidly re-allocating resources and leveraging the organizational capabilities and capacities to compete based-on experiences.

This research is an empirical study, but the results of Collaborative Networked Organizations (CNOs) and Virtual Customer Communities show low results so that they are unable to influence marketing performance. Further research is suggested to re-examine the model with a wider range of respondents, in a broad collaborative organization so that it can be generalized more broadly. This study has not discussed the effect of value co creation on consumer experience. As we all know that experience is the result of the acceptance of value added by consumers. So that further research can examine the effect of value creation on the experience of using the product.

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